

Evaluation of Wind Field Reconstruction for Lidar-Assisted Control of a 2 MW Wind Turbine

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Abstract: Lidar-assisted control of wind turbines is a promising technology for reducing the structural loads on wind turbines. The load reduction can then lead to an extended service life, minimization of operating costs and noise, as well as an increase in energy production. Reliable and accurate wind preview is essential for this technology. As only the wind speed in the line-of sight can be measured, the wind field must be reconstructed using wind and lidar models and estimation algorithms. In this work, we analyze the data availability and evaluate the wind preview quality of a baseline wind field reconstruction methods using measurement data from a lidar installed on the nacelle of our 2 MW research wind turbine. As a reference, a rotor-effective wind speed estimate is obtained from turbine data in real time. For this purpose, a reduced model of the drivetrain dynamics including mechanics and electrics as well as aerodynamics is developed based on a complete aero-elastic wind turbine model. This model is then used in an immersion and invariance estimator. A tuning method is developed to achieve a fixed estimation delay over the entire operating range. This estimator then enables the determination of the prediction time of the lidar-based estimation of the rotor-effective wind speed. Furthermore, the estimator enables an evaluation of the wind preview quality, represented by the coherence between the lidar-based and turbine-based estimation of the rotor-effective wind speed. The analysis of data over more than one year shows that the data availability depends on the measurement distance as expected, but also on the mean wind speed. Further, the wind preview quality and the prediction time correspond to the expectations from the theoretical models and change only slightly during the analyzed period.

1 Introduction

Lidar-Assisted wind turbine control (LAC) has first been successfully tested in 2012 [SCH14]. In 2020 the milestone of one thousand wind turbines 3 GW using this technology has been reached¹. Important challenges are still the complexity of the certification and the proof of robustness.

This work aims to contribute to this development by highlighting the robustness of the technology in an industrial application over a longer period.

The work is organized as follows: Section 2 provides background information on our project and our wind turbine and lidar system. In Section 3 describes the estimation method of the wind preview from turbine and lidar data. Section 4 provides the results of the availability and wind preview quality and Section 5 concludes the work and provides an outlook to future work.

¹ <https://www.sowento.com/important-milestone-reached-for-lidar-assisted-control-of-wind-turbines-1000-wind-turbines/>

Figure 1: Wind turbine MM92 with two nacelle-based lidar systems. The right-hand lidar system (looking towards the rotor) was used in the following analysis.

2 Measurement Setup

In this section, our research project and the setup of our experiment are introduced.

2.1 ABBA Project

The “ABBA” project aims to develop adaptive strategies for the operation of existing wind turbines in order to ensure that they can be adapted to current and future challenges. In particular, the focus is on improving wind field reconstruction for real-time applications, developing optimized feedforward control strategies and validating these approaches on a real wind turbine. The use of the improved wind field reconstruction is aimed at providing more precise input variables for lidar-based control, with the objective of increasing energy yields, reducing mechanical loads for extending the operational design life of the turbines and noise emissions.

2.2 Test Turbine MM92

The MM92 is an onshore wind turbine from REpower (later Senvion and today Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy) that has been in production since 2005 and is used as a representative existing turbine for the investigations within the project. With a rated power of 2.05 MW, a hub height of 100 m, and a rotor diameter of 92.5 m, it offers good conditions for validating the strategies developed to optimize the operation of existing turbines. The turbine is located outside several neighboring wind farms in the north of Schleswig-Holstein near Flensburg. The area is characterized by a flat topography with mainly agricultural land.

2.3 Nacelle-Based Lidar System and Data Acquisition

The data acquisition for the wind field reconstruction was performed by one of the two installed nacelle-based lidars. The lidar used is an NL200 from Nanjing Movelaser (see Figure 1). The system measures in a range of 50 m to 200 m with maximal 10 measurement distances and a sampling rate of 4 Hz. It has four pulsed beams that are arranged at a horizontal angle of $\pm 15^\circ$ and a vertical angle of $\pm 12.5^\circ$. The lidar data, together with a selection of turbine data, were transferred to a small single-board computer (Revolution Pi) and merged. The data is stored in binary files formatted to comply with OpenFAST standards. The 10-minute data files are transferred to a server via a data access service once a day. In total, 23730 data files from September 2023 to March 2024 and 6779 data files from December 2024 and January 2025 were analyzed for this study. In the months in between, the data collection wasn't possible.

Figure 2: Setup of I&I wind speed estimator (left). Response to wind steps (right).

3 Methodology

This section describes how the rotor-effective wind speed (REWS) is estimated based on turbine and lidar data and how the two signals are then used to calculate the wind preview quality.

3.1 Wind Speed Estimation from Turbine Data

In simulations, the REWS is typically calculated from the turbulent wind field by the mean of all longitudinal wind components hitting the rotor disc [SCH15]. The best measurement device for the REWS for real experiments is the wind turbine itself. Typically, a “torque-balance” wind speed estimator is used to calculate in real-time the REWS v_0 from turbine data such as rotor speed Ω , pitch angle θ , and generator torque M_G [HOO04; HEL19]. Therefore, a simplified wind turbine model is used, where J is the rotor inertia, M_a the aerodynamic torque, r_{GB} the gearbox ratio, and the mechanical and electrical losses M_{loss} :

$$J\dot{\Omega} = M_a(\theta, \Omega, v_0) - (M_G + M_{loss}(M_G, \Omega))r_{GB}. \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Due to the cubic wind speed relationship of the aerodynamic torque, this estimator requires solving a cubic equation. This is typically done a priori and then in a real-time application a 3D interpolation with signals of Ω , θ , and aerodynamic torque $M_a = J\dot{\Omega} + (M_G + M_{loss})r_{GB}$ is used. The main shortcomings are the difficulties in finding the correct solution of the 3 possible ones and the discretization for the interpolation.

Here, the “immersion and invariance” (I&I) wind speed estimator is used based on [LIU22]. It uses a baseline proportional-integral (PI) controller and the simplified turbine model from Eq. 1, see Figure 2 (left). Here, the real wind turbine is controlled by (here unknown) feedback controller using the demanded pitch angle θ_c and demanded generator torque M_{Gc} and distributed by the REWS v_0 . The input to the PI controller is the difference between the measured rotor speed Ω and the estimated one $\hat{\Omega}$. The output of the PI controller is the estimated wind speed \hat{v}_0 . The measured pitch angle θ , generator torque M_G and \hat{v}_0 are the inputs to the wind turbine model of Eq. 1, which provides the estimated rotor speed $\hat{\Omega}$.

The advantages of this method are that it can be easily implemented and tuned. The transfer function G_E between the real wind speed v_0 and the estimated wind speed \hat{v}_0 and be simplified and then compared to the desired behavior with the desired damping D and frequency ω :

$$G_E = \frac{K_P b_2 s + b_2 K_1}{s^2 + K_P b_2 s + b_2 K_1} \stackrel{!}{=} \frac{2D\omega s + \omega^2}{s^2 + 2D\omega s + \omega^2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

This results in the following equations for the proportional gain K_P and the integration time T_I :

$$K_P = -\frac{2D\omega}{b_2} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$T_I = \frac{K_P}{K_I} = \frac{2D}{\omega} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The only turbine parameter needed is here $b_2 = \left. \frac{\partial \dot{\Omega}}{\partial v_0} \right|_{OP}$, which depends on the operation point (OP). However, it can be approximated to 0.03 rad/m for the given wind turbine. With $D = 0.7$ and $\omega = 1$ rad/s, the resulting wind speed estimator provides an almost constant response to wind speeds at 4 m/s (region 1.5), 8 m/s (region 2), and 12 m/s (region 3), see Figure 2 (right).

3.2 Wind Speed Estimation from Lidar Data

Lidar systems measure a projection of the wind speed called the line-of-sight wind speed (v_{LOS}). This magnitude must be processed to estimate the characteristics of the wind field, and this process is called wind field reconstruction (WFR), which is applied using specific models and assumptions of the lidar measurements and the wind field [BOR17]. The WFR methodology used in this work estimates the REWS using a simple point measurement model of a fixed lidar at the hub height. The methodology assumes perfect alignment between the wind and the turbine as well as linear vertical and horizontal shear. For the purpose of LAC, the rotor-effective wind speed (REWS) must be estimated at every acquisition time. Therefore, the methodology reconstructs the REWS by dividing v_{LOS} of every measurement by the cosine of the angle-to-centerline and computing the mean over the last four estimated longitudinal wind components.

3.3 Comparison of Estimated and Analytic Coherence

The coherence between the rotor-effective wind speed of the turbine and the lidar estimate serves to evaluate the quality of the wind estimation obtained from the lidar measurements. Additionally, an analytical coherence model based on wind spectra such as the Kaimal can be used as reference for comparison with the measurement estimated coherence. In this work, the analytical coherence model proposed by [SCH13] is used as reference. On the other hand, the coherence γ_{RL}^2 estimated from the measurements is obtained using the equation:

$$\gamma_{RL}^2 = \frac{|S_{RL}|^2}{S_{RR}S_{LL}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Where S_{RL} , S_{RR} and S_{LL} are the cross-spectrum between both signals and the auto-spectrum of the signal from the turbine and the lidar, respectively. These magnitudes are calculated from the measurements, considering ten-minute segments of the data.

Most part of the analytic model are depending on space, rather than time. Therefore, the analytical coherence for different mean wind speed is usually very similar displayed over wave number. The wave number k can be calculated from the frequency f with the mean wind speed \bar{u} :

$$k = \frac{2\pi f}{\bar{u}}. \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

Figure 3: LOS-availability for all beams and different wind speeds (top left), for all beams, the 2nd wind bin and different periods (top right), and for all wind speeds and different beams (bottom left). REWS-availability (bottom right).

4 Results

This section provides detailed results of the availability and wind preview quality.

4.1 Availability

For availability, we differentiate availability for line-of-sight (LOS) and rotor-effective wind speed (REWS).

For the LOS availability, the number of available LOS measurements is divided by the total number of LOS measurements within 10 min. The LOS availability is mainly impacted by two effects: the blade blockage and the reduction of data availability with increasing distance due to the reduced number of returning photons. Figure 3 (top left) illustrates the two effects: overall data during normal operation, the blade blockage is reducing the availability to around 65 % (extrapolating the blue line towards 0 m/s). The overall data availability is further reduced to around 50 % for the last distance. When the data are divided into three wind bins from 6 m/s to 10 m/s, 10 m/s to 14 m/s, 14 m/s to 18 m/s, we observed that the availability is reducing with increasing wind speed. The data for the bin 10 m/s to 14 m/s are divided in three different periods, see Figure 3 (top right): the availability is relatively constant over the full campaign, with a slight reduction over the last two months. We will continue to monitor the availability to detect any further reduction. In Figure 3 (bottom left), we then divided the full data set into the 4 different beams, illustrating the impact of the blade blockage: since the bottom beams are cutting the rotor disc closer to the hub, the blades cover these beams longer during operation.

Finally, Figure 3 (bottom right) depicts the REWS availability, defined as the number of time steps where the internal WFR is able to provide a REWS divided by the total number of time steps. The REWS availability is significantly higher than the LOS availability, but still wind speed dependent.

Figure 4: Comparison of the estimated wind speed from turbine data and lidar data for three exemplary 10-minute periods.

4.2 Wind Preview Quality

The estimation of the REWS from turbine data and lidar data described in Section 3.1 and Section 3.2 is then applied to all data. Figure 4 shows an example for three exemplary 10-minute periods. The preview of the lidar signal is clearly visible as well as the high correlation of low frequencies and the low correlation of high frequencies as predicted by the correlation model from Section 3.3.

We then calculated the auto-spectra of the linearly detrended two signals for every full 10-minute block as well as the cross-spectra between the two signals. No windowing or overlapping was used. The spectra are then averaged over wind bins from 10 m/s to 16 m/s with a bin width of 2 m/s, where again only data is used where the turbine was running in normal operation, ending up into 2951, 1415, 865, and 323 blocks for 10 m/s, 12 m/s, 14 m/s, and 16 m/s, respectively. For the binning, the mean of the REWS from the turbine data was used. With the averaged auto-spectra and cross-spectra, the coherence is then calculated.

In Figure 5, the coherence is displayed over wave number exemplary for the 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th distance at 64 m, 92 m, 120 m and 148 m. As expected, the coherence is very similar for all 4 wind bins, even that the REWS availability drops significantly over wind speed, see Figure 3. This motivates the use of adaptive Filtering as explained in more detail in [SCH15]: for higher mean wind speeds less filtering is necessary based on Eq. 6.

Further, the coherence at 64 m and 92 m is better than the expected value from the analytic model. We assume that the wind evolution is either overestimated for these distances or the impact of possible yaw misalignment is less impactful for these distances.

Figure 5: Coherence between rotor and lidar estimated REWS for several wind speed bins over the full campaign compared to the expected analytic model.

5 Conclusions and Outlook

This work presents a evaluation of wind field reconstruction for lidar-assisted control of a 2 MW wind turbine over a longer period of time. For the evaluation, an estimator of the rotor-effective wind speed from turbine data is developed and tuned such that the signal is delayed by a constant time.

The evaluation reveals that the line-of-sight availability depends as expected on the location of the lidar on the nacelle and the measurement distance. Additionally, a clear mean wind speed dependency could be detected. The rotor-effective wind speed availability also depends on distance and mean wind speed and is between 60 % (far measurement and high wind speeds) and 100 % (close measurement and low wind speeds).

The evaluation of the wind preview quality however reveals that the wind preview quality in terms of measurement coherence is not impacted by the lower availability and is close to the expected values, even better as expected for distances close to the rotor.

Future work includes a more detailed analysis of the wind preview quality with respect to inflow angle, turbulence class, and advanced wind field reconstruction methods. Further, several lidar-assisted control methods will be tested including collective pitch, multivariable and optimal feedforward controller.

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